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**MODERN STUDIES OF PERSONALITY.
INTERDISCIPLINARY PARADIGMATICS OF DIFFERENTIAL
PSYCHOLOGY**

Relevance of the topic. Modern life under conditions of a rapidly developing technocratic civilization calls on special demands on the depth and content of scientific personality understanding. The main brunt of new personological concepts development has been traditionally put on differential psychology, which is a discipline of individual differences. How should the list of these differences be formed? What are the criteria of the completeness of such a list? How are these differences interconnected one with each other? The answers to these questions lie in the scope of concretization and structuring of the differential psychology subject matter field, definition and localization of its paradigms. In fact, this is one of the fundamental methodological problems, namely, the localization of the ontology of the investigated reality. We associate the solution of this problem with the use of the structural-ontological approach used in interdisciplinary research to describe the structure and functioning of complex systems (Shymko, 2020).

Statement of the main material. In order to determine the ontological boundaries of the system (personality) under consideration and the structural understanding of its paradigmatics, we have developed and proposed the corresponding structural ontological matrix. It graphically displays the system-forming factors, the interaction of which constitutes the personality, determining the composition, structure, functional design and features of the system genesis (Fig. 1). So, the horizontal axis of the matrix represents the *material of the system* – the individual psyche with its fundamental dichotomies (subjectively experienced phenomena and behavior). The vertical axis represents the *primary process of the system* – the interaction of the psyche with the environment in which the personality functions and develops (biophysical properties of the environment and social culture). Please note that the layout of the axes might be different and

depends on the theoretical preferences of the scientist or the goals of a particular study.

In the proposed version, the segments of the structural-ontological matrix reflect the paradigmatics of differential psychology. Namely, the first segment corresponds to the molecular-biological paradigm of understanding individual differences. The second segment is associated with the worldview diversity of personality. This area is mainly associated with a cognitive-psychological approach. The third segment corresponds to the socio-psychological paradigm. Fourth – associated with a body-oriented approach to the psychology of personality.

Fig. 1. Structural-ontological matrix of the subject matter field of differential psychology.

Analyzing the proposed structural ontological matrix (Fig. 1), we would like to focus here on the following aspects, in our opinion, of great importance for the research practice. Namely, the biggest prospects for modern differential psychology lie in the field of understanding the interconnections between the presented paradigms. Against the background of the classical interest in neurophysiological patterns (segments 1 and 4, Fig. 1) and the relatively recent

surge in research attention to neuro-cognitive problematics (segments 1 and 2, Fig. 1), a role of social semantics (segments 2 and 3, Fig. 1) and its influence on differential psychological patterns - are at the very beginning of scientific comprehension. The understanding of the sphere of “social physicality” (segments 3 and 4, Fig. 1) remains even less developed, pioneering updating of which we are obliged to the French anthropologist Michel Foucault (1977).

Conclusions. The modern outlook on personality, in our opinion, should be characterized mainly by an interdisciplinary orientation. Wholistic study of the personality, as well as individual differential psychological phenomena and effects, must be organized taking into account a systematic understanding of the personality nature and the laws of its functioning.

References

1. Shymko, V. (2020). Introduction to structural-ontological methodology: analysis of the subject matter field of personality socialization. [Online]. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3575800>
2. Foucault, M. (1977). Discipline and Punish. New York: Pantheon Books.